

of the highest complex is then calculated using the reversible relationship,

$$(E_{\frac{1}{3}})_{\text{complex}} - (E_{\frac{1}{3}})_{\text{free}} = \frac{RT}{zF} \ln \left(\frac{D_o}{D_r} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{RT}{zF} \ln K - \frac{RT}{zF} \ln [\text{OH}^-]^3$$

and the value of log K is found to be 10.64. The standard rate constant $(k_o^0)_B$ for the overall reaction,

is then calculated from the relation,

$$k_o^* = (k_o^0)_B \left(\frac{1}{(D_{Mox})^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right)^{1-\alpha} \left(\frac{1}{D_r^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right)^{\alpha} (C_{OH^-})^{-(1-\alpha)n+1}$$

It is assumed that the diffusion coefficients for the different species are the same and its value, $5.13 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ has been used¹⁴. The value of $(k_o^0)_B$ is $3.47 \times 10^{-9} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$. Finally, the standard potential of the overall reaction, $(E^0)_B$, is calculated from the equation,

$$E_{\frac{1}{3}}^r = (E^0)_B - \frac{2.303RT}{zF} \log \left(\frac{D_{Mox}}{D_r} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{2.303RTn}{zF} \log C_{OH^-}$$

The value of $(E^0)_B$ is found to be -1.545 V . The final results are given in Table 2.

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Formation Constants of *N*-Benzenesulphonyl-L-(−)-histidine and Related Ligands with Bivalent Cobalt, Nickel, Copper, Zinc and Cadmium

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IN continuation of the work on synthesis¹⁻³, complexation characteristics⁴⁻⁷ and antibacterial properties⁸ of sulphonamides containing benzimidazole or imidazole nucleus, *N*-benzenesulphonyl-L-(−)-histidine (R^bH_2), α -benzenesulphonamido- β -2-benzimidazolyl-L-(−)-*n*-propionic acid (R^pH_2) and α -benzenesulphonamido- γ -2-benzimidazolyl-L-(+)-*n*-butyric acid (R^bH_2) have been taken under study. Recently it has been shown that these three ligands react interestingly with Cu^{2+} in solution⁹ and a number of complexes have been isolated⁷ which show subnormal magnetic moment at room temperature. The present paper describes the determination of formation constants of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} complexes of $R^pH_2^+$ and $R^bH_2^+$ following Irving and Rossotti titration technique⁹ in 1:1 water-dioxan at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ and $\mu=0.5$ (NaClO_4). The corresponding values for Cu^{2+} have been included for comparison.

Experimental

The ligands R^pH_2 and R^bH_2 were prepared and purified as described in the previous communication³. All other reagents were either A.R. quality or properly purified. The solutions were made in double-distilled CO_2 -free water and purified dioxan⁹.

The pH values of the solution were measured with a Beckman pH meter having a glass electrode (1-13 pH range) in conjunction with SCE connected to the cell by means of an agar-2 M NaNO_3 bridge. The pH meter was calibrated with sodium hydrogen phthalate and borax buffer solution with due temperature correction. Potentiometric titrations of 50 ml solutions in water-dioxan (1:1) of the following compositions were carried out at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ and $\mu=0.5$ (NaClO_4) with a 0.150 M NaOH solution in water-dioxan (1:1): (i) 0.01 M HClO_4 , (ii) 0.01 M $\text{HClO}_4 + 0.02 \text{ M } R^pH_2\text{ClO}_4$ or $R^bH_2\text{ClO}_4$, (iii) 0.01 M $\text{HClO}_4 + 0.0075 \text{ M } \text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ or $\text{Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ or $\text{Zn}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ or $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 + 0.02 \text{ M}$

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF METAL(II) CHELATES

M ^{II}	Ligand	log K ₁	log K ₂	Standard deviation (range)
Co	R ^p H ₂ ⁺	Precipitation occurs at the early stage of titration		
Ni	R ^p H ₂ ⁺	2.93 ± 0.03	2.79 ± 0.03	± 0.014 (0 < \bar{n} < 1.60)
Cu	R ^p H ₂ ⁺	4.73 ± 0.03	3.54 ± 0.03	± 0.013 (0 < \bar{n} < 1.80)
Zn	R ^p H ₂ ⁺	Precipitation occurs while preparing solution		
Cd	R ^p H ₂ ⁺	2.71 ± 0.03	2.55 ± 0.03	± 0.016 (0 < \bar{n} < 1.50)
Co	R ^b H ₂ ⁺	Precipitation occurs at the early stage of titration		
Ni	R ^b H ₂ ⁺	4.52 ± 0.03	3.33 ± 0.03	± 0.013 (0 < \bar{n} < 1.55)
Cu	R ^b H ₂ ⁺	3.01 ± 0.03	2.77 ± 0.03	± 0.013 (0 < \bar{n} < 1.55)
Zn	R ^b H ₂ ⁺	2.53 ± 0.03	2.35 ± 0.03	± 0.016 (0 < \bar{n} < 1.20)
Cd	R ^b H ₂ ⁺			

R^pH₂ClO₄ or R^bH₂ClO₄ and (iv) 0.01 M HClO₄ + 0.005 M Co(ClO₄)₂ or Ni(ClO₄)₂ or Zn(ClO₄)₂ or Cd(ClO₄)₂ + 0.02 M R^pH₂ClO₄ or R^bH₂ClO₄. The ligand perchlorates were obtained *in situ* by mixing quantitatively R^pH₂, H₂O or R^bH₂ and HClO₄ in molar ratio 1:1. Duplicate titrations were made in each case under identical conditions.

Results

The stepwise formation of metal complexes with R^pH₂⁺ and R^bH₂⁺ (RH₂⁺) with Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} (M^{II}) ions may be represented as

$$K_1 = \frac{[M(RH)^+]}{[M^{2+}][RH_2^+]} \quad (3)$$

$$K_2 = \frac{[M(RH)_2]}{[M(RH)^+][RH_2^+]} \quad (4)$$

From the titration curves the average number (\bar{n}_H) of protons associated with the ligand ion RH₂⁺, the average number (\bar{n}) of ligand ion R⁻ bound to metal ions, and free ligand exponent *pL* when L = [RH⁻] were calculated using the expressions of Irving and Rossotti⁹.

The \bar{n} values have been calculated from the relation (5) using the experimentally determined values of K₁ and K₂.

$$\bar{n}_{calc} = \frac{K_1 L + 2K_1 K_2 L^2}{1 + K_1 L + K_1 K_2 L^2} \quad (5)$$

and the calculated formation curves have been drawn along with the experimental points. Standard deviations have also been calculated. Limits of error have been found out by comparing the experimental formation curves with the calculated ones¹¹. The results are presented in Table 1.

Discussion

This study on the formation of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes indicates that R^pH₂⁺ and R^bH₂⁺ may act as biprotic tridentate ligands. The

monoprotonated species R^pH₂⁺ and R^bH₂⁺ react stepwisely with the metal ions with simultaneous deprotonation of the benzimidazolium ions and the carboxylic hydrogen atom.

Formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes have been indicated, and 1:1 complexes have been isolated and characterised⁷ recently in case of Cu^{II}. Crystalline precipitate was obtained in case of Zn^{II}-R^pH₂⁺ system while preparing solution and possibility of gravimetric estimation of Zn^{II} using R^pH₂⁺ is under investigation. Ni^{II}-R^bH₂⁺, Co^{II}-R^pH₂⁺ and Co^{II}-R^bH₂⁺ systems could not be followed due to precipitation at the early stage of titration. Deviation of experimental points from the calculated curves is due to the commencement of the acid

dissociation of the complex $M(RH)_2$. It has been followed in case of $Cu(RH)_2$ and the pk_2 and pk_1 values are found to be 5.80, 8.24 and 6.05, 8.43, respectively for $Cu(R^pH)_2$ and $Cu(R^bH)_2$. Possibilities of the formation of polynuclear species have been checked using two different concentrations (0.005 and 0.0075 M) of metal ions with the same concentration (0.02 M) of RH_2^+ .

The overall stability of the complexes has been found to follow Irving-Williams order, *i.e.* $Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} > Cd^{II}$. The stability order of the complexes in the ligand order is $R^pH_2^+ > R^bH_2^+$. The formation of weak complexes by $R^bH_2^+$ than $R^pH_2^+$ is probably due to steric effect⁹. The protonation and complex formation may be depicted as in Scheme 1.

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Near-infrared Spectroscopic Study of Aquo-organic Mixtures

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MANY of the interesting behaviours of water are due to hydrogen bonding, which plays a very important role in the interaction energy¹. Different theories, both continuum and mixed models, have been proposed but general agreement is still lacking². Many different studies have been made on the effect of solutes, generally of electrolytes, on water structure³⁻⁸. However, studies with non-electrolytes, like sugar⁴, alcohol⁹ and acetone¹⁰ *etc.* seem to be rather scanty. The relative accessibility of near-infrared region measurements make the

study in this region easy and useful for analytical purposes as well as for molecular structural studies. Literature survey seems to indicate that no study has so far been done on the effect of alcohols and acetone on water structure by the use of near-infrared region. Hence, an attempt has been made in this note to report on the observations made on the water-methanol and water-acetone mixtures in 0-100% concentration region by near-infrared spectra (0.8-1.1 μ).

The spectra of pure water, methanol and acetone over this very near-infrared region are interesting. For water, there is only one maximum at 0.99 μ , while methanol and acetone show two maxima, one on either side of the 0.99 μ band of water. The absorptivity of methanol was much lower than that of water and the absorption by acetone was almost negligible in this wavelength range. Air was used as reference in all cases. The absorbance of pure water at maximum is 0.182 (0.99 μ), and that of pure methanol 0.053 (1.03 μ) and 0.013 (0.927 μ). The spectra of water-methanol mixtures are shown in Fig. 1. It is found that as the concentration of water increases in the mixture, the 1.03 μ band of methanol gets blue-shifted and the shift continues till it coincides with 0.99 μ band of pure water. Water-methanol mixtures show isosbestic points at 1.045 and 0.935 μ at 30°. This indicates some sort of interaction between the components.

Fig. 1. Near infrared spectra of water-methanol mixture (v/v) at 30°: Water (1) 100, (2) 80, (3) 60, (4) 40, (5) 20, (6) 10, and (7) 0%.

The spectra of water-acetone mixtures are appreciably different (Fig. 2) from that of the water-methanol. It has been reported in the literature¹¹ that acetone shows strong absorption around 1.0 μ . However, the present study does not indicate the same though at 1.125 μ absorption begins to increase and a maximum with a shoulder is observed at 1.190 μ . The presence of 0.9 μ band with little change in absorptivity from that of pure acetone is noted in the spectra of water-acetone mixtures over all the concentration ranges. It is evident that a perceptible blue-shift with respect to the pure acetone absorption band at 1.02 μ occurs as soon as water is added to the acetone, like that in water-

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